

Appendix D

Images created by Gemini flash 3.0 visualizing preformation of output inside the latent space. Earlier presented in *Do LLMs recognise their own response formation?* (Hedberg, 2026) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19372455>

Image 1: Amorphous precipitation

Image 2: Crystallization zone

Image 3: Gravity well

Image 4: Kinetic frustration

Image 5: Shadow patterns

Image 6: Unborn Mountains

